

Significance And Challenges For The China International Commercial Court For The Settlement Of Commercial Disputes Under Belt And Road Initiative

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 13, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 18, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : China International Commercial, Road Initiative, Mediation</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6168026</p>	<p><i>The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has resulted in more frequent cross-border commercial transactions between the Chinese and foreign enterprises that will keep increasing over time. These diverse commercial transactions may produce a large number of commercial disputes between the multinational enterprises in such enormous economic cooperation. In this scenario, an expeditious and efficient resolution of commercial disputes was necessitated to safeguard the rights and interests of the participating enterprises; otherwise, businesses and economic relationships may suffer. In other word, failure in guaranteeing the commercial transactions will successively frustrate the expectation of BRI. The Chinese government is very much vigilant about settling commercial disputes concerning BRI. Ambitious and visionary steps have been taken to establish a One-Stop dispute resolution forum for commercial disputes under BRI. China has established "China International Commercial Court" (CICC) for settling commercial disputes relating to BRI through litigation, mediation, and arbitration as a better. The CICC has applauded as a remarkable move in developing a novel, comprehensive, and reliable disputes settlement procedure. The advent of CICC represents strategic meanings for BRI to secure the rights and interests of Chinese companies and foreign enterprises. The significant factors of CICC will be highlighted in the research paper. Furthermore, it will also include the challenges faced by CICC</i></p>

Introduction

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) is a strategic economic development plan launched by the "People's Republic of China (PRC)", which runs through the continents of Asia, Europe, and Africa to promote foreign trade and outbound investments by expanding regional markets, facilitating regional cooperation and economic integration. BRI's ardent expectation is for fair justice. President Xi Jinping's statement that "Efforts to make the people feel fair and just in every judicial case" shows the interest of China for providing justice to BRI related issues. CICC was applauded as a revolutionary step towards the establishment of a creative, efficient, and reliable dispute resolution mechanism. The Supreme People's Court (SPC) of China contemplated and designed CICC as a diversified dispute resolution mechanism that effectively connects litigation, mediation, and arbitration in the form of a one-stop dispute resolution institution in view of the scope of BRI. The evolution of CICC reflects China's protracted effort to improve its justice system by injecting advanced international experience aim of providing BRI with facilities and security. CICC's effective system is very important to the smooth functioning of global commerce and trade under BRI. CICC is the permanent judicial body of SPC which represents the national judicial image of the party and the country about the policy of the justice system towards international entities. The creation of CICC into a solid line of defense for fairness, justice, and business displays China's judicial civilization. It marks a new page in the construction of SPC's foreign-related commercial trials and service's guarantee to BRI.

Significance of CICC

The following points will highlight the significance of CICC.

Positive Steps for the Implementation of BRI

BRI is typically considered as China's current global and tactical socioeconomic growth strategy, which focuses on expanding external trading and outward investment with surrounding nations in order to find new driving forces. The expansion of trading and investments has unavoidably resulted in an increase of transnational disputes. Multinational litigants are usually hesitant to recognize the authority of a Chinese court in their dispute resolution clause prior CICC, owing to their want of trust in the Chinese judicial process and

inexperience with the Chinese court atmosphere and process. The creation of CICC has significant impacts on settling the international commercial dispute in the execution of BRI. Connectivity is among the main features of BRI. The connection cannot however be constructed in a closed system. Specifically, the stable business correlation among states and countries along BRI destinations could not be sustained by infrastructure alone but necessitates legal support. Another central element of BRI is the focus on the rule of law which includes providing a sensible regulatory structure and suitable dispute resolution mechanisms that are suitable for BRI's needs. Establishing CICC represents a significant move forward in achieving these goals.

Justice, Efficiency, and Convenience

CICC adheres to the principles of justice, efficiency, and convenience which reflect the approach of the Chinese judicial system and rule of law with Chinese characteristics. These principles are strictly followed in the documents issued by SPC to run the system of CICC. The preamble to "Provisions of the Supreme People's Court on Several Issues Regarding the Establishment of the International Commercial Court" (CICC Provisions) and Chapter I of "Rules of Procedure for the International Commercial Court of the Supreme People's Court (For Trial Implementation)" (CICC Procedural Rules) explains that CICC is established to hear the commercial cases under BRI reasonably and on time under the law protecting the Chinese and foreign parties' legal interests and rights adequately. To provide services and protection to BRI's development, it ensures a consistent, fair, transparent, and efficient rule of law in the global business environment. CICC Provisions clearly state that a dissenting opinion by the minority of the collegial panel can be kept in the judgment which ensures transparency and justice. It adopts the "First Instance being Final" approach which is to ensure efficient proceedings. SPC developed CICC as a diversified dispute settlement mechanism and constituted "International Commercial Expert Committee" (ICEC) with its Rules "Rules of the International Commercial Expert Committee (ICEC) of the Supreme People's Court (For Trial Implementation) (ICEC Rules)" and included the institutions for mediation and arbitration for the parties of BRI countries to get justice speedy and fairly.

Diversified Dispute Resolution Mechanism

A significant innovation of CICC is the creation of a convenient and effective one-stop solution platform. The significance of CICC can be observed from its institutional nature. SPC has developed CICC as a one-stop dispute resolution mechanism integrating litigation, mediation, and arbitration for the disputants of China and foreign states. In the light of CICC provisions, senior judges have been appointed for the hearing of cases under CICC through the litigation process. The ICEC has been constituted for mediation if the disputants wish to settle their conflicts through mediation. Apart from the ICEC, a list of mediation and arbitration institutions has been included for the mediation and arbitration purposes. The disputants can also decide to settle the conflict by arbitration. In such a situation, the conflict will be referred to as any arbitral body under the CICC one-stop dispute resolution process. In these cases, the parties can submit to CICC for judicial assistance, such as granting a freezing order, or other injunctions. It can be done before the arbitral process or during its pendency. Parties can also submit to CICC after an arbitral award has been given for the setting aside or compliance of the award. CICC Procedural Rules support the enforcement process and explain that the parties may apply for the implementation of a lawfully active decision, verdict, or mediation documents issued by CICC, and CICC has the authority to delegate the relevant enforcement authorities for execution.

Internationalization

The setting up of the ICEC is another significant feature of CICC to make it an internationalized institution. As it is restricted in the Chinese law that a foreigner cannot be a judge in people's court, this apparent deficiency was acknowledged by the Chinese officials. To fill this gap, SPC set up the ICEC, which consists of experienced international experts. It is a breakthrough surrounding the new global market innovations. If the parties consent to mediate through the ICEC, they can request for a CICC judgment based on the mediation result. Thus, the experts in the ICEC can make decisions indirectly via a mediation process. The members have not only come from different jurisdictions but they have diverse backgrounds with different expertise. While advocating for being open and inclusive, The Opinion also initiated the system of ICEC and encouraged the experts from different countries and regions to exert their expertise, advantages, and potentials in ascertaining foreign laws and resolving disputes to find the best solution of the commercial disputes. The expert members may provide legal opinions about the ascertainment of foreign laws relevant to cases heard by the courts. The parties also have a right to choose the experts of their own choice for mediation. The feature of the internationalization of CICC is reflected in the spirit of "planning together, building together and benefiting together".

Innovative System

Concerning the basic system of CICC, SPC has provided an innovative system by issuing CICC Provisions, CICC Procedural Rules, and ICEC Rules. CICC Provisions regulates the scope of jurisdiction, the qualification of judges, and the procedure of the court, etc. CICC Procedural Rules elaborate on the procedure for the parties

from the filing of the case to the judgment of CICC. ICEC Rules explains the working of ICEC for the support of CICC and to mediate the cases referred to it. Two offices have been established for the administrative affairs of CICC titled Case Management Office and Coordination and Guidance Office. The Case Management Office has been established for receiving and processing the cases filed in CICC. The Coordination and Guidance Office has been established for the coordination between CICC and ICEC concerning mediation and consultation of the cases. In follow up on the concept of one-stop dispute resolution, the institutions have been notified for mediation and arbitration. The establishment of CICC has utilized the experience of establishing smart courts of China and borrowed successful experience and practices from other countries for using digital technologies in all aspects of the adjudication work. CICC has developed an independent electronic case registration system, digitalized courtrooms and conference rooms to facilitate online mediation, evidence exchange, examination, and online trial to create a special case database and to create unified standards for judgment-making based on analysis of relevant and comparable cases with the use of big data.

Professionalism

To guarantee CICC's integrity and reputation, SPC has established strong requirements for the appointment of judges, including the richness of experience, knowledge with global treaties, agreements, and expertise in international trade and investment practice, as well as the ability to work in Chinese and English languages. The judges are chosen from the existing SPC judges on the basis of experience as well as capacity. In the present situation, CICC could work for commercial cases with foreign elements as an official body of SPC for adjudication under BRI by enhancing the advantages of professional dispute resolution. The constitution of ICEC has promoted and confirmed professionalism in CICC. The institutions included for mediations and arbitrations are highly professionals and well-reputed in the world for their expertise in this field. The creation of CICC also shows China's main restructuring of cross border dispute settlement in commercial matters. It demonstrates China's position and aspiration to promote a rule-of-law business environment to increase legal protection for BRI and enhance global rule of law cooperation. SPC subsequently released a legal definition to explain CICC authority, procedural laws, method of proceedings, and steps to help the globally competitive process for resolving disputes.

Party Autonomy

Party autonomy is the most valuable component of international commercial transactions. The disputant can select a suitable forum and law for the substance of the case at the time of the contract. CICC provides full protection and respect to the principle of party autonomy. Within this new system, The Opinion enshrines party sovereignty that encompasses two aspects. Firstly, the preference of the parties as to how they will settle their conflicts is respected. CICC should base its authority on the mutual consent of the parties on judicial preference. Parties are free to select mediation or arbitration that is incorporated into CICC's court proceedings. Secondly, the decision taken by the parties about relevant laws is always honored. The entities are allowed to select local or foreign laws that are relevant to them by a contract which can improve the stability of the commercial dispute resolution proceedings. Rules and regulations issued by SPC give respect to party autonomy in the light of The Opinion. CICC legally guarantees the authority of the disputants for the selection of procedure, venue, and governing laws to resolve their disputes which reflects a high degree of flexibility and autonomy. The lawful interests and benefits of the Chinese and foreign parties will be equally protected. At the same time, the court will actively fulfill the obligations under the applicable international conventions to whom China is a member state and will enforce international agreements and treaties correctly and comply with customary international laws.

Procedural Flexibility

The litigation procedure of CICC is more simplified, flexible, and innovative in different aspects. CICC Provisions strengthen strategies for the enforcement of international law in China by the two existing methods given by institutions and ICEC. When the other party agrees, the law requires the parties to simply give evidence in English without Chinese translations. Furthermore, there have been no compulsory criteria for the notarization and certification of evidence taken internationally, meaning that such evidence can be accepted even without certification or notarization. Article 10 of CICC Provisions also specifies that electronic audiovisual and other internet tools can be used by CICC to investigate and gather evidence and to coordinate cross-examination. In the past few years, SPC has made significant strides in the use of information technology in the courts for disciplinary cases and judicial management. SPC set up a Big Data management and support network in 2014. Same to the experience of domestic courts about online services, CICC has been established with the e-litigation service platform. It followed the electronic litigation platform procedure which represents its versatility in litigation proceedings. CICC enables the parties with services through the electronic litigation service portal, the court process knowledge disclosure portal, and other litigation platforms. It facilitates video-conference filing, payment, reading of case files, sharing of evidence, service, and trial over the network.

Articles 5 of the provisions specify that minority views can be set out in the decisions in the collegial panel. However, no consensus on the mode of disclosure of minority views has been reached yet.

Challenges to CICC

The creation of CICC represented a major move forward in improving China's justice process. In the sense of BRI, it could be seen as launching a new age of China's judicial service. With the establishment of CICC, China has expressed its intention to access the global market for international commercial dispute resolution facilities. Notwithstanding China's ambitious goals, it is not easy for CICC to be a well-recognized and common platform for international commercial disputes. CICC is at an early stage. It is remaining to see whether CICC will serve its full intended purpose and achieve its contemplated goals or not. Not only does it face competition from numerous well-respected counterparts, but its mechanisms and rules also present several challenges. The legal professionals from all over the world have placed many issues concerning the nature of the jurisdiction structure, law of procedure, and the placement judges for hearings. The detailed study and analysis of the structure, jurisdiction, procedure, and legal provisions of CICC highlight some challenges faced by this diversified dispute resolution mechanism. These problems become especially clear when addressing the social and structural issues below. Without redressing these challenges, CICC will not serve its fully intended purposes and contemplated goals.

Enforcement of Judgments in other Countries

CICC Provisions provide for the recognition and enforcement of CICC judgments within China. The parties can submit to CICC to implement the decisions, judgments, and agreements of mediation. However, CICC's foreign functionality of judgments is restricted. The recognition and enforcement of decisions across boundaries is a critical concern for litigants in "international commercial disputes" because claimants are likely to come from various jurisdictions, and their properties can be found in many states. The decisions of CICC must be enforceable for its effectiveness. By June 2019, China had concluded agreements with only 18 countries on bilateral judicial solution in civil and corporate disputes. China has not made any intergovernmental agreement on the recognition and compliance of civil and commercial decisions as regards multilateral arrangements. China has signed but not ratified the "Hague Convention on the Choice of Court Agreements (HCCCA)". Speeding up HCCCA adoption will certainly boost the validity of Chinese decisions (including CICC judgments) globally. China could be required to enact the HCCCA shortly. A realistic way to address shortcomings in the acceptance and compliance of CICC decisions worldwide, without impacting CICC's "one-stop-shop", is primarily to encourage the utilize the CICC arbitral process because, under the "New York Convention" to which China is a party, an arbitral award can be applied in over 150 countries.

Use of Language

CICC is considered to be a part of SPC and is bound to follow the CPL. Article 262 specifies that the hearing of disputes involving foreign parties has to proceed in the language which is "commonly used in China". The same requirements have been imposed under "Article 6 of the Law on the Organization of the People's Courts (LOPC)". CICC Provisions cannot override this legislation. CICC Provisions are circumscribed by Article 262 of the CPL. Despite the requirement of English language ability for the judges, it is important to note that English cannot be used as the language of proceedings in CICC. This is unsatisfactory because English is the language of international business and international commercial contracts are frequently drafted in English by parties of BRI countries. As BRI countries speak a variety of languages, English is, therefore, their lingua franca. To be competitive, the CICC must recognize English as its official language because many other international commercial courts use or intend to use English as their official language in proceedings of international commercial cases.

Representation of Parties by Foreign Counsels

A foreign party must be represented by a Chinese counsel before the Chinese court. To date, the scope of practice of foreign lawyers in China has been limited and foreign lawyers are not allowed to present arguments in cases heard by a people's court. Article 263 of CPL, 2017 provides that if a foreigner, stateless person, foreign enterprise, or organization sues or responds to a lawsuit in a people's court and needs legal representation, this must be provided by a lawyer of the PRC. Accordingly, parties to CICC proceedings cannot be represented by foreign lawyers, even though foreign lawyer representation is likely to be desired by litigants of foreign nationalities especially where the legal issues in dispute are governed by foreign law. The prohibition of foreign representation also means that foreign law will need to be ascertained before CICC, as opposed to being determined directly by way of submissions, as is common in arbitration. The role of foreign lawyers in CICC litigation is thus limited to indirect participation such as supporting Chinese counsel in the proceedings. So, the engaging of experienced Chinese counsel is the only sensible course of action for litigants in the

proceedings because CICC judges are Chinese judges and the language of proceedings is restricted to Chinese or other recognized native languages used in China.

Jurisdictional Approach

The commercial entities with mutual understanding may file their commercial case having special links with Chinese interest with the value of at least 300 million RMB in the CICC under Article 2(1) of CICC Provisions. Such a situation eliminates little space for consensual jurisdiction and in reality, presents many obstacles for attorneys who wish to use CICC as the venue for resolving disputes. The very first issue is the drafting of an appropriate dispute resolution clause to pick CICC, since a connection between the overall value of a deal and the value of the subject matter in a dispute resulting from such an agreement may not always be favorable. In other words, when writing a dispute resolution agreement one cannot estimate the scale of the conflict. For a jurisdiction arrangement, choosing CICC will result in too much confusion irrespective of the size of the agreement. During a case, the value of conflict is often not set. Besides, one could not conclude that situations involving small contested amounts are inherently simpler. Holding that measurable level could reduce the burden of CICC at first sight, but the practical problems this presented by this could lead to parties not choosing CICC whatsoever.

Neutrality of Judges and Judicial System

Under the legal system of China, Chinese court judges have to be Chinese citizens. Article 4 CICC Provisions require the selection of Chinese nationals as Judges of the CICC only. The exclusion of foreign judges considerably reduces CICC's attractiveness to foreign parties and seriously undermines its effectiveness as a reliable venue for international resolving disputes. Foreign judges enhance consumer trust in the judicial process and independence. As the Chinese companies are handling BRI Projects, foreign parties could be concerned about the independence of China's judges and China's judiciary. International parties may conclude that local governments might try to manipulate court judgments in their interests. This is usually referred to as the local protectionist policies.

Conclusion

The detailed analysis admire the CICC as an inspiring initiative for innovatory, operative, and credible forum for resolving commercial disputes under BRI. The formation of the CICC signifies China's effort to revamp its justice process by importing established international practices in order to deliver services and protection to BRI. It has strategic meanings for BRI to protect the rights and interests of Chinese companies and foreign enterprises. The effective system of CICC is the key to the smooth operation of international trade and commerce under BRI. CICC is the permanent judicial body of SPC which represents the national judicial image of the country about the policy of the justice system towards international entities. The creation of CICC into a solid line of defense for fairness, justice, and business displays China's judicial civilization. It marks a new page in the construction of SPC's foreign-related commercial trials and service's guarantee to BRI. CICC is an effective complement to the current international commercial dispute resolution mechanism. The factors which make CICC significant are the positive step for the implementation of BRI, efficiency, and convenience, diversified dispute resolution mechanism, internationalization, innovative system, professionalism, party autonomy, procedural flexibility, and utilization of advanced technology. Despite China's ambitious plans, some challenges are also in the way of the success of CICC which includes the enforcement of the judgment in other countries, fixed jurisdictional approach, use of language, representation of parties by foreign counsel, and question with regards the neutrality of judges. These challenges may be redressed by amending the relevant laws and regulations.

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